

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

PhD Researcher (Technical Textiles), Thesis-final part
School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
(Funded by Australian Government Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
M.Tech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
Bachelor of Science in Textile Engineering
City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Consultant (Textile coloration, Defence textiles, Technical textiles)
Office: 512.01.12, 25, Dawson Street, Brunswick, Vic-3056, Australia
engr.anowar@yahoo.com +61 452209738, +8801788396264

Lecturer (study leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
Newcastle University College, Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
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Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying and Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka
Former Dyeing Officer, Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka

Anowar's Handbook on Garments Manufacturing Technology

Md. Anowar Hossain

School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh

(engr.anowar@yahoo.com)

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Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, MTech
PhD Researcher, ID: 3820066
(Funded by Australian Government Scholarship)
School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University
512.01.12, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick
Vic-3056, Australia.

Key note of handwritten book

This preprint book is helpful for production engineers, textile engineers, garments designers, fashion designers, students, researchers, professors and professionals in the field of garments and textile engineering. This handbook is written from author's notebook for exam preparation in Bachelor of Science in Textile Engineering.

Author information

Md. Anowar Hossain

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<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>

www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Md. Anowar Hossain, Anowar's Handbook on Garments Manufacturing Technology, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh; 17 May 2023.

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Tex-306 : Garments Manufacturing Technology

Course instructor: Jemifar Amman
(B.Sc in Textile)

Write down the flow chart of sample garments manufacturing?

Design: Production depends on :-

- Self imaging power
- To copy some design
- To modify previous design.

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Basic block :

Basic block is the part of human body's pattern which is made without any allowance.

Pattern :

Any parts of garments size in flat paper / template.

Sample approval :

When the order is confirmed by customer then it send to the customer for approval. Customer check the garments according to their required quality. [Such as garments, size, color, fastness property, hand feel etc] If customer approved the sample then go for bulk production and the sample which is approved/OK by customer is called approve sample.

~~***~~ Show the different parts of a shirt?

Ans :

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Fig: Different parts of a shirt

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*** Discuss about costing of a garments ?

Ans: Generally the costing of a components are grouped under four headings.

Such as:

- (1) Direct material cost
- (2) Labour cost
- (3) Factory over head
- (4) General over head.

Direct material cost:

Direct material cost are all the materials and trimmings (পোষাক প্রস্তুতকরণ জিনিস) which go into the construction and finish of the garments. Typically, these materials would include cloth, lining, buttons, zippers, labels, hangers and packaging materials etc.

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Labour cost:

This covers the cost of all the labour directly involved in producing the garment and could include cutting, fusing, regular sewing, pressing, finishing, final inspection and packing. Labour of all types and grades have a direct overhead which includes holiday pay, sick pay etc and the legal payments made by the employer for each employee. This is usually expressed as a percentage of salary and when this percentage is added to the employee's wage, it becomes the basis for calculating direct labour cost.

Factory overhead: There are different methods of calculating the factory overhead, but most of them use a combination of the following three items:

(1) **Indirect Labour:** This covers the every person in the factory who does not directly perform a production operation, such as: Managers, time keeper, clerk, maintenance staff.

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(2) indirect materials : It is also known as consumables, this element contains all materials not directly connected to the make-up of a garments. Some of these typical materials are m/c sparte parts, paper, markers, chalk, pins etc.

(3) Other expenses : Included in this element is very fixed and variable expense in operating the factory such as rent, rates, utilities, insurance, maintenance and the various types of energy generation required by a clothing factory.

General overhead : The general overhead comprises all the labour costs and expenses which are need in running the company such as : management, marketing, finance, warehousing, rent rates etc.

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*** What do you understand by Markkerz ?

Ans: Markkerz is a large paper which contains all the different sizes of pattern for a particular style of garments. This paper is called markkerz.

*** Write down the requirements of markkerz planning

Ans: Markkerz planning is a conceptualising, sensitive, open and creative process. In order to plan efficiently it is necessary to visualise the markkerz as a whole to see it at a glance, the planner proceeds by first positioning the largest pattern pieces in a relationship which looks promising and then fitting the smaller pieces into the gaps. Moreover the following point should be considered during markkerz making:

1. Fabric width গাঢ়তা = যা ২৭ মত্রে
৫২৫ ২৫
2. Markkerz length/width
3. Number of pieces of markkerz.
4. No of sizes of markkerz.
5. Types of garments
6. Size of garments
7. Types of fabric

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Constraints/Barriers of marker making:

1. Grain line: Every pattern pieces must have grain line. Grain line indicates the warp/wale direction of fabrics.

2. Nature of fabrics: If the fabric is symmetric then there is no problem to make marker. If the fabric would be asymmetric then it create great problem to make marker. i.e check, strip, printed fabric.

3. Design of Statements: It need mirror effect that means require to look some appearance between left and right side.

4. Cutting quality:

ⓐ For the majority of cutting situations where a knife blade is used, the placement of the pattern pieces in the marker must give freedom of knife movement and not

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restricted the path of the knife. So that it leads to accurate cutting.

(b) A pattern count must always be made at the completion of the planning of a market to check that the complete menu of patterns have been included. This is not just for a formality when, for instance a 12 garment trousers market, where each garment may have 16 pattern pieces, signifies a complete market of 192 pattern pieces.

(c) Correct labelling of cut garment parts is essential if, in sorting and bundling a multi size lay after cutting, operators are to identify correctly the parts which make-up whole garments. It is the responsibility of the market planner to code every pattern piece with its size as the market is marked.

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5. Production planning :

When an order is placed for quantity of garments, it normally specifies a quantity of each size and color, the former often gives a ratio. For example, an order being placed in dozens, 500 dozens of a T-shirt may include 200 dozen red, 200 dozen blue and 100 dozen green across sizes 15s, 16s, 18s and 20s in the ratio 2:4:4:2. The shirt maker will also require a marker and in the above example the marker planner may make two markers. Each marker contains six garments, one with two size 15s, two size 16s and two size 18s and other with two sizes 16s, two sizes 18s and two sizes 20s.

~~***~~ Write down the efficiency of marker?

$$\text{Marker efficiency} = \frac{\text{Total area of pattern in marker}}{\text{Total area of marker}} \times 100$$

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*** Write down the methods of market making?

- (1) Manual
- (2) Computerized

Merits of computerized market making:

- (1) Especially suitable for large scale products.
- (2) Checks/strippes can be viewed and adjusted.
- (3) Grading can be done automatically and instantly.
- (4) Lay planning can be rearranged within a short.

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Demerits of computerized market making:

- (1) More skill labour required
- (2) Not appropriate for small quantity garments prodⁿ.
- (3) Expensive than manual market making.
- (4) Satisfactory plan of design can not be obtained.

Quiz

~~Q~~ What do you understand by fabric spreading?

Ans:

Fabric spreading: Fabric spreading is a process by which we can spread the fabric as per the dimension of the market.

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During spreading, the number of lay should not be more than 200. It depends on the -

- (1) Fabric thickness
- (2) The height of the knife
- (3) Volume of production

(4) Type of fabric (slippery, tough)

*** Write down the basic requirements of fabric spreading?

Ans:

(1) Alignment of fabric plies: All plies must be aligned in one side and comprised at least the length and width of the marker plan. But should have the minimum extra outside of those measurements.

(2) Correct ply tension: If the plies are spread with too slack a tension, they will lie in ridges with irregular shape. On the other hand the plies are spread in a stretched state, they will maintain

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enr.anowar@yahoo.com +61 452209738, +8801788396264

Lecturer (study leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
Newcastle University College, Chittagong
Newcastle University College, Chittagong, Bangladesh
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their tension while held in the lay, but will shrink after cutting and during sewing. Thus the shrinking garments parts to be smaller size than the pattern size.

Elimination of fabric faults:

Fabric faults (hole, stain etc.) may be identified by the fabric supplier and additional faults may be detected during examination of the fabric by the garments manufacturer prior to spreading.

Elimination of static electricity:

In spreading piles of fabric containing man made fibres, friction may increase the charge of static electricity in the fabric. Friction may be reduced by changing the method of threading of fabric through the guide bars of the spreading m/c.

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

PhD Researcher (Technical Textiles), Thesis-final part
School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
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Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
M.Tech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
Bachelor of Science in Textile Engineering
City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Consultant (Textile coloration, Defence textiles, Technical textiles)
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Avoidance of distortion in the spread: A layer of glazed paper, laid glazed side down, is normally placed at the bottom of the spread.

→ It helps to avoid disturbing the lower plies of material in the spread when the base plate of a straight knife passes.

→ It prevents snagging of the fabric on the table surface.

Avoidance of fusion of plies:

→ Fabric may fuse together during cutting if the cutting knife becomes hot as a result of friction with the fabric.

→ Anti-fusion paper may be used. It contains a lubricant which lubricates the knife blade as it passes through the spread, thus reducing the increase in temp. of the blade arising from friction.

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Automatic spreading process:

1. Spreading is possible by robotic technique.
2. Fabric spreading sensor checking system is available by photo sensor cell.
3. Speed of spread is controlled by this method.
4. This method has roll turning arrangement. Automatic loading and unloading device present for fabric roll.
5. Ply is no is automatically set.
6. Automatic tensioning device is present.
7. Auto leveler used to align the fabric selvages.
8. Any crease or fold in the fabric is removed by this method.
9. Length of spread is automatically maintained as per previously length of lot.

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

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10. Automatic cutting device is present
at the end of the spread.

Q. Write down the object of cutting?

Ans: To make a complete garments, cutting
is necessary from the spread of fabric as
per the dimension of marker.

Q. Write down the requirements of cutting?

Ans:

1. Precision of cut: Fabric will be cut at
the actual line of marker. It depends on

2. Methods of cutting employed line of
marker. It depends on:-

→ 1. Methods of cutting process

→ 2. Marker planning - distance
between two pattern pieces.

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Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTEchin Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
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- (1) Markert making
- (2) Condition of cutting equipment
- (3) Clean edge
- (4) Unfused edge
- (5) Support of the lay.
- (6) Consistent of cutting
(সামঞ্জস্যপূর্ণ)

*** Write down the methods of cutting ?

Ans:

- (1) Manual : completely manual
- (2) Manually operated powered knife
- (3) Computercized method

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*** Discuss about Manual methods of cutting?

Ans:

Scissor is used to cut fabric in this method.
Scissor can be used to cut one or two no of ply by proper practice, precision of cut can be obtained.

Disadv:

- (1) More time is required to cut fabric.
- (2) Cost is high to cut fabric per garments.
- (3) Wastage of fabric is high.

Adv:

- (1) Investment cost low.
- (2) Suitable for small production.

*** Write down the classification of manually operated powered knife.

Ans:

- (a) Rotary blade or round knife
- (b) Straight knife
- (c) Band knife
- (d) Die water

Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain

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*** Write down the features of Rotary knife ?

Ans:

1. Blade is octagonal
2. Blade is driven by electric power.
3. Very sharp edge blade : Blade dia 2 to 8 inch, thickness 0.5 to 1 mm.
4. Grinding wheel attached on the blade.
5. Blade can be lubricated by attached soaking oil.

Fig: Rotary knife

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

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Advantages:

- (1) Suitable to cut single ply
- (2) Suitable for small production
- (3) Suitable for gentle curve cutting

Disadvantages:

- (1) Limited ply of fabric can be cut.
- (2) Not suitable for large production
- (3) Not possible to cut very sharp corners
- (4) Difficult to cut very small pieces of pattern
- (5) Possibilities of accidents are high.

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Fig: straight knife.

In garments industries, it is the most commonly used knife. Two main parts of this m/c are:

(i) Head

(ii) Base plate.

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

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Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
M.Tech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
Bachelor of Science in Textile Engineering
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4. There are wheels under base plate to move the knife over cutting table easily. It contains electric motor at the top of the stand. The stand is attached with base plate. There exists a handle with head and it has reciprocating motion. By means of hand, the knife as well as motor can be moved according to cutting direction. A grinding wheel attached besides the straight knife which is used to sharpen the knife during cutting.

Two motions are needed to cut fabric by straight knife. They are:

- (a) The motion that reciprocates the knife at very high speed.
- (b) The motion that helps to move the cutting knife in fabrics lay in different direction.

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Precaution to avoid blade deflection:

- (1) Reducing the height of lay.
- (2) Holding the handle carefully.

Features of straight knife:

- (1) Blade height or length 10 to 13 cm
- (2) Blade width : 1 to 1.5 cm
- (3) Blade thickness : 0.5 to 1.0 mm
- (4) Parts: Motor, grinding wheel, knife, base plate, handle, stand etc.
- (5) Blade can be sharpened by attaching wheel.

Adv. of straight line:

- (1) High cutting speed
- (2) Sharp corners (corners) can be cut

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(3) Possible to cut all pattern pieces directly from the fabric spread.

(4) Suitable for bulk production.

(5) Have blade sharpening arrangement.

Disadvantages:

(1) In case of high lay height, blade direction may be occurred due to operation negligence.

(2) Possibilities of accident high.

Q: Discuss about Band knife?

Ans: Band knives are used when a high standard of cutting accuracy is required than straight knife, when small parts

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such as collar, cuffs and pockets are cut, a template of metal in the shape of the pattern piece may be clamped to the section of lay on top of marker.

Then the knife cutting exactly along the hatched edge. (Band)

Features of Band knife:

- (1) Endless loop of flexible blade
- (2) Thinner than straight knife
- (3) Blade is driven by electric power
- (4) Blade is stationary whereas the fabric moves
- (5) Block/locked pieces required to cut the component.

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~~Write~~ Write down the difference between
straight knife and Band knife.

1. Band knife is more used in manweaving

2. Blade is driven by electric power

3. Thinner than straight knife.

4. Suitable for cut small component.

5. Used for special purposes

6. More accuracy

7. low speed

1. straight knife is more used in all purpose.

2. Blade is not driven by electric power.

3. Blade thickness 0.5 to 1mm.

4. Suitable for bulk production.

5. Possible to cut all pattern pieces

6. less accuracy.

7. high speed

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one side of the fabric to the width of the fabric
~~Write down~~ Write down the advantages of Band knife
and dis-adv.

Advantages:

- (1) Used for special purposes
- (2) Get more accurate cutting than straight k
- (3) Suitable for cut small component
- (4) Suitable to cut very sharp corners

Disadvantages:

- (1) Not suitable for large production
- (2) Work load is high due to stationary cutting
- (3) Fabric wastage high.

The result of cut is...
N = ...
Result of leaf...

Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain

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Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
M.Tech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
Bachelor of Science in Textile Engineering
City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Consultant (Textile coloration, Defence textiles, Technical textiles)
Office: 512.01.12, 25, Dawson Street, Brunswick, Vic-3056, Australia
enr.anwar@yahoo.com +61 452209738, +8801788396264

Lecturer (study leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
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Newcastle University College, Chittagong
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Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain

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3. Feasible for very large scale production

4. Can be joined directly into marker

fibre making system.

5. Speed of cutting can be controlled.

6. Cutting defects are less than other method

7. Blade sharpening arrangements are available.

Disadv:

1. Very expensive method

2. Higher maintenance cost.

Write down the features of table of

knife cutter.

Ann:

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① Table is perforated
② Table is covered with Nylon filament bed.
③ A beam moves between x-axis and the cutting head moves between y-axis
④ At the underneath of the table, air suction unit is available.
⑤ A monitor and operator switches are placed on any side of the table.
⑥ This is divided into two parts, one is feed side and another is delivery side.
Write down the principle of water jet cutting.
Ans: Fabric is cut by highly pressurized water jet emitting out from a very fine nozzle. The pressure created about 60,000 psi/inch². This high pressure is responsible for cutting; the

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enr.anowar@yahoo.com +61 452209738, +8801788396264

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The pressurized jet works as a sharp instrument when it passes through fabric. The cutting efficiency can be changed by changing water jet speed/pressure. A plate is kept under the lay to collect or take water which is called catcher.

table and to reduce water sound)
Fig: Water jet

~~Task~~ Write down the advantages and disadvantages of water jet cutting.

Ans:
Advantages: (1) Specially used for wood cutting

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common, front and cover word
CAM (computer aided) Manufacturing system

includes:

① Auto spreader

② Auto cutter

Q. Discuss about LASER cutter?

Ans:

Feature:

① Dia is 0.25 mm

② Cutting head is controlled by computer.

③ Light is reflected on to the fabric and then the fabric is cut.

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

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There are Six Final Exam

Name of course instructor:
Hossain Anwar Hossain, B.Sc in Textile

For this style, new colour P.N composite
APs Group.

Reference Books:

- (1) Garments manufacturing Technology - Karshom
- (2) The technology of clothing manufacturing Hatold Carter and Barbara

*** what do you understand by sewing?

Sewing: joining of fabric by needle and thread is called sewing. It may be one or more layers of fabric.

Alternative method:

- (1) Moulding : Ladies, babies
- (2) Fusing
- (3) Welding : Ladies, Babies.

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Write down the better joining method of needle and thread?

Ans: Seam: The line of joining fabric is called seam. Sewing is the most important step in garments manufacturing, it is the domestic process of garments assembling and still the best way of achieving both strength and flexibility.

Write down the properties of seam?

Ans: Success of seam is considered by-

→ Appearance of seam

→ Performance of seam.

Appearance of seam: Good appearance in a seam normally means smooth joining of fabric with out fabric damage and uneven or minded stitch.

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Performance of Seam:

Performance of seam depends on -

- (1) Strength of joint
- (2) Elasticity
- (3) Durability
- (4) Security
- (5) Comfort
- (6) Special feature

Write down the factors affecting the properties of seam.

Answer:

1. The seam type which in a particular configuration of fabric.
2. The stitch type which in a particular configuration of thread in fabric.

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(b) The sewing ~~or~~ feed mechanism, which is moves the fabric past needle and enable succession of stitch to be formed.

(c) The needle which insert the thread into the fabric.

(d) The thread which forms the stitch, which either holds the fabric together neatens it or decorates it.

Write down the types of Seam?

100 types of Seam, 1956 years B.S.A →

British standard Association made

8 types :

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

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Make necessary Adjustments: Adjust

- (1) Superz clam-1 (Superz imposed seam) 30
- On a few occasions - occasionally 35
- (2) Superz clam-2 (Lapped seam) 45
- (3) Superz clam-3 (Borend seam) 50
- (4) Superz clam-4 (Flat seam)
- (5) Superz clam-5 (Decorative seam)
- (6) Seam clam-6 (Edge retexturing)
- (7) Seam clam-7 (Edge stitch seam)
- (8) Seam clam-8 (The enclosed seam)

Seam clam-1 :

- 1. The fabric ends should be in same side from seam line.
- 2. Seam thickness is equal to the two ply fabric.

Use :

Trousers making, shirt etc. apparel manufacturing.

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Seam class-3:

1. At least two piece of fabrics is needed for board seam formation.
2. One of the fabric board the opened end of other pieces.

uses:

1. Board seam is used for decorate garments.
2. It is used more in knit than woven.
3. Most secured seam.

Seam class-4:

1. Seam thickness is equal to fabric thickness.
2. Two ply of fabric cannot overlap but they have spaced between them.

Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain

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Subject: Selection Body Complex
(3) Flat seam strength is less than other
from seam: seam seam seam

(4) Without increasing the thickness of
ply, seam is produce.

Seam class-5 :

1. By stitching one or more layers of fabric side by side, this seam is produced.
2. For produce this seam multi-needle sewing eye and folder is used.
3. This seam is used mainly for decorative purpose.

Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain

PhD Researcher (Technical Textiles), Thesis-final part
School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
(Funded by Australian Government Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
M.Tech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
Bachelor of Science in Textile Engineering
City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Consultant (Textile coloration, Defence textiles, Technical textiles)
Office: 512.01.12, 25, Dawson Street, Brunswick, Vic-3056, Australia
enr.anwar@yahoo.com +61 452209738, +8801788396264

Lecturer (study leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
Newcastle University College, Chittagong
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Seam class-6:

- 1. This seam is mainly use for edge neatening process i.e the raw edge of fabric does not come out.
- 2. For proper joining of fabric.

Seam class-7:

Criteria:

Seam of this class adds in separate item to the edge of garments parts. They are similar to the lapped seam except that the added component has a definite edge on both side.

Uses:

This types of seam may be use to attach lace, elastic braid etc.

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

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Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTEchin Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
Bachelor of Science in Textile Engineering
City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Consultant (Textile coloration, Defence textiles, Technical textiles)
Office: 512.01.12, 25, Dawson Street, Brunswick, Vic-3056, Australia
engr.anowar@yahoo.com +61 452209738, +8801788396264

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City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
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Fibre length: The distance
Here, a twin needle sewing m/c with a ¹⁰⁰⁰mm
between the ends of fibres, which
folded is use for this reason.

Seam class-8: ① In this seam class only
one piece of fabric needs to be involved in
constructing the seam.

② Many of these seam requires compli-
cated foldings prior to sewing.

Use: The most common seam type in this
class is the waist loop as jeans, rain-
coats etc.

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enr.anowar@yahoo.com +61 452209738, +8801788396264

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*** what do you understand by seam-type?

Ans: Arrangement of fabric ends at the different seam line, is called seam type.

*** what do you understand by stitch?

Ans: When sewing loop or loops of a one or more thread binds with each other by interlacing, interlooping or interlocking or combination of those, each unit of such configuration is called stitch.

*** what do you understand by interlacing?

Ans: When one thread passes over another thread to bind with each other is called interlacing.

*** what do you understand by interlooping?

Ans: When loops of one thread passes through the loops of another thread to form stitch is called interlooping.

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Q: What do you understand by intralooping?

Ans: When a loop of one thread passes through the loop of same thread to form a stitch is called intralooping.

Q: What do you understand by stitches type?

Ans: There are about 70 stitches type. Among this 20 stitch type are used most commonly. This 20 stitches are divided in 6-classes. Each class is called stitch class.

Q: Write down the classes of seam & stitch.

Ans:

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- (1) Stitch class - 100 (single thread ^{clean} class stitch)
- (2) Stitch class - 200 (hand stitch)
- (3) Lock stitch class - 300 (lock stitch)
- (4) Stitch class - 400 (multi thread chain stitch)
- (5) Stitch class - 500 (over edge stitch)
- (6) Stitch class - 600 (covering chain stitch)

Stitch class-100 :

- (1) It is formed by interlooping technique.
- (2) Only needle thread is needed for stitch formation.
- (3) Security of stitch is very low.
- (4) Used for temporary joining of fabric.
Also use for gathering effect in the apparel.
(গুলাকরা)
- (5) In this class, stitch type-103 is used for attaching button and, making button holes and for blind hemming.

Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain

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Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

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occurrence of ...
authentic ...
in the ...
is reduced ...
the ...

- (5) Limited length of sewing can be done at a time.
- (6) It is use mainly for sewing costly dress.

Stitch-209

Stitch-class-200 :
(200-299)

Stitch type-201

of fibre ...
...

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

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1. Stitches under this class are formed by two groups of thread. Upper thread is called needle thread and lower thread is called bobbin thread.

2. Stitch is formed by interlacing.

3. Strength and extensibility is sufficient.

4. Extensibility of lock stitch is normally about 36%.

5. Appearance of both stitch is exactly same in both side.

6. Stitches under this class are secured. Security of stitches could be further increased by back-tacking in both starting and finishing end.

7. Frictional resistance of this stitches are very good.

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Former Dyeing Officer, Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka

Line :

Stitch-clam-300 is extensively used for general sewing woven garment production. Attaching collar, cuff, pocket, bottom holding etc purposes.

Stitch clam-400 :

Stitch type - 401

- (1) At least two groups of thread are needed.
- (2) Upper thread is called needle thread and under thread is called looper thread.
- (3) Stitch formed by interlacement and interlooping.
- (4) From top side look like lock stitch but from under side double chain appearance is observed.

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engr.anowar@yahoo.com +61 452209738, +8801788396264

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Former Dyeing Officer, Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka

5. Possibility of seam pucker is less than lock stitch.

6. Speed is higher and stoppage time is lower.

7. stitch type 401 is the most common among 400 groups.

Use :

- 1. Suitable for sewing long length.
- 2. Suitable for sewing heavy fabrics.

Stitch class : 500

stitch type : 504

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

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Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
M.Tech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
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1. Stitches conduct this clam is formed by two or more groups of thread.

2. At least one group of thread passes over the cut edge of fabric staying is protected by this clam of stitch.

3. stitch could only be formed at the edge of the fabric.

4. Extensibility may be upto 300%.

5. stitch type 504 is shown in the sketch formed by one needle thread and two looper thread.

uses:

Extensively used for knit garments.

Production and also used in woven garments.

garments.

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

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(Funded by Australian Government Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
Bachelor of Science in Textile Engineering
City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
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from a sample of 100 fibres if
Stitch class - 600:

would be approximately 1000
groups of fibres
thousand

Stitch type - 602

- ① Stitches under this class are formed by at least three groups of thread.
- ② One thread is called needle thread, one group is called top cover thread and other group is called bottom cover thread.
- ③ No of thread may be upto 9 in case of stitch type - 606.

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

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School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
(Funded by Australian Government Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
M.Tech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
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(4) Stitch type 606 is known as flat lock and used in knit garments manufacturing.

(5) Stitches under 600 class is used mainly in knit wear manufacturing.

~~Ans~~ Write down the types of sewing m/c.

Mainly two types of sewing m/c.

(a) Manually operated sewing m/c.

(b) Electrically operated sewing m/c.

The sewing m/c which are used in industry is called industrial sewing m/c. The different industrial sewing m/c are

1. lock stitch m/c

2. chain stitch m/c

3. over lock m/c

4. Zigzag stitching m/c

5. Flat lock m/c

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

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- 6. Blind stitch m/c
- 7. Button holing m/c
- 8. Button attaching m/c
- 9. Barstek m/c

*** write down the manufacturer company
list

Ans:

- 1. Juki (Germany)
- 2. Pfaff
- 3. Pegasus
- 4. Singer
- 5. Brother
- 6. Seruba

*** write down the function of sewing m/c
needle?

Ans: 1. To make hole in fabric without damaging
the threads. so that the needle and thread can
pass through fabric.

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② After penetration of fabric, to form a needle thread loop which will be picked-up by the rotating hook or looper.

③ To pass the needle loop through the under thread loop.

*** Write down the component of needle and function of each component? ***

Fig: Needle.

Butt: Conical shape at the top of the needle to attach the needle with needle holder.

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Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
Bachelor of Science in Textile Engineering
City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Consultant (Textile coloration, Defence textiles, Technical textiles)
Office: 512.01.12, 25, Dawson Street, Brunswick, Vic-3056, Australia
enr.anowar@yahoo.com +61 452209738, +8801788396264

Lecturer (study leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
Newcastle University College, Chittagong
Newcastle University College, Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former chief executive officer, Bangladesh textile and fashion, Uttara, Dhaka
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Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying and Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka
Former Dyeing Officer, Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka

Shank: May be circular or half circular.

It give support to the needle.

Shoulder: Shoulder is inclined (slanted) portion between shank and blade. It expand needle hole in fabric.

Blade: It is the longest and finest portion of needle blade is generally tapered to top.

Long groove: In blade there is a elongated groove, in which thread lies during stitch formation.

Short groove: It lies on the side of needle eye. It helps the needle thread in loop formation.

Eye: Needle eye is important and sensitive component of needle. Needle thread pass through it.

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain
PhD Researcher (Technical Textiles), Thesis-final part
 School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
 (Funded by Australian Government Scholarship)
 Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
 Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 M.Tech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
 Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
 University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
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 City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
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 Office: 512.01.12, 25, Dawson Street, Brunswick, Vic-3056, Australia
 engr.anowar@yahoo.com +61 452209738, +8801788396264

Lecturer (study leave), Department of Textile Engineering
 City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
 BCME College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
 Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
 Newcastle University College, Chittagong
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Ques: Describe about needle size?

- Ans: 1. Mettric System.
 2. Singert System.

Mettric system:

Needle blade diameter x 100

= 9 mm x 100 = 90 Nm

Singert system: 9, 10, 11, 12

Here, 12 → coarse

9 → fine

Mettric (Nm) → Singert

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

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Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
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enr.anowar@yahoo.com +61 452209738, +8801788396264

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*** Write down the object of sewing thread feed mechanism?

Ans:

- Step 1. To make good appearance and performance of seam by sewing
2. To avoid seam pucker.
 3. To feed the fabric sewing m/c uniformly
 4. To control the speed of fabric
 5. To avoid any stitching defect.

*** Write down the parts of feed mechanism

Ans: Sewing m/c feed mechanism consist of the following three parts:

1. Throat plate.
2. Feed dog
3. Pressure foot.

Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain

PhD Researcher (Technical Textiles), Thesis-final part
School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
(Funded by Australian Government Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTEchin Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
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City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
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Office: 512.01.12, 25, Dawson Street, Brunswick, Vic-3056, Australia
engr.anwar@yahoo.com +61 452209738, +8801788396264

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Throat plate:

1. Throat plate is made of stainless steel and its surface is made very smooth to feed the fabric easily.
2. There are one or more than one slot in the throat plate into which feed dog moves forward and backward.
3. There is also a hole (which is called needle hole) in the throat plate through which the needle up and down.

Feed dog:

1. The main task of feed dog is to move the fabric to predetermined length.
2. Stitch length regulator controls the movement of feed dog.

Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain

PhD Researcher (Technical Textiles), Thesis-final part
School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
(Funded by Australian Government Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
M.Tech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
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3. Feed dog has toothed surface in upper part which rises through the slot in the throat plate, touches the under surface of fabric and move fabric one step forward. Then feed dog drops down, below the throat plate. Thus its operational cycle is completed. For one cycle, one stitch length will be fed.

4. The up and down movement of needle should be carefully synchronised with the elliptical motion (timing) of feed dog, so that fabric can move forward when needle is out of action.

5. The pitch distance (distance between the two consecutive teeth point) range of feed dog for different fabrics are as follows.

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

PhD Researcher (Technical Textiles), Thesis-final part
School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
(Funded by Australian Government Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
M.Tech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
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Pitch distance and length of thread
1.3 - 1.6 mm → For light to medium weight fabric.
1 - 1.25 mm → For very light weight fabric.
1.7 - 2.5 → For heavy fabric.

Q. Write down the types of feed mechanism?

Ans: There are six types of feed mechanism.

1. Drop feed mechanism
2. Differencial bottom feed mechanism.
3. Adjustable top feed mechanism.
4. Needle feed mechanism.
5. Union feed mechanism
6. Puller feed mechanism.

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

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Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
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Figure of drop feed mechanism is given below:

Fig: Drop feed mechanism.

Description of drop feed mechanism:

1. It is the simplest and most used feed mechanism.
2. During sewing of fabric plies (2) by drop feed mechanism, feed dog moves the lower ply forward and the upper ply also gets motion due to contact and pressure with lower ply.

Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain

PhD Researcher (Technical Textiles), Thesis-final part
School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
(Funded by Australian Government Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
M.Tech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
Bachelor of Science in Textile Engineering
City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
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Office: 512.01.12, 25, Dawson Street, Brunswick, Vic-3056, Australia
enr.anwar@yahoo.com +61 452209738, +8801788396264

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3. The main disadvantage of drop feed system is plugging. Skilled operator can remove this problem but speed of the sewing m/c is slow.

Q: What do you understand by Trimmings?

Ans: Content of fabric use inside fabric/ garments, is called trimmings.

Q: Write down the list of trimmings?

- Ans:
- | | |
|---------------------------|-----------------------------|
| 1. Thread | 8. Motif (Design of fabric) |
| 2. Button | 9. Lace-braid - Elastic |
| 3. Interlining | 10. Wadded |
| 4. Lining | 11. Shoulder pad. |
| 5. Label | |
| 6. Zipper | |
| 7. Hook and Loop fastener | Lace → ডিপ |

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

PhD Researcher (Technical Textiles), Thesis-final part
School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
(Funded by Australian Government Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
M.Tech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
Bachelor of Science in Textile Engineering
City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Consultant (Textile coloration, Defence textiles, Technical textiles)
Office: 512.01.12, 25, Dawson Street, Brunswick, Vic-3056, Australia
engr.anowar@yahoo.com +61 452209738, +8801788396264

Lecturer (study leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
Newcastle University College, Chittagong
Newcastle University College, Chittagong, Bangladesh
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Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying and Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka
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Q. What do you understand by accessories?

Write down a list of accessories.

Ans: Content of fabric packaging use outside of fabric/ garments is called accessories

List of accessories are-

1. Hang tag.
2. Poly bag.
3. Brass pin/ Ball head pin
4. Scotch tape.
5. Back/ Neck board
6. Hanger
7. Timure paper
8. Plastic clip (with/ without teeth)
9. Gum-tap.
10. Carton.
11. Strapping belt
(Poly propylene belt)

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

PhD Researcher (Technical Textiles), Thesis-final part
School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
(Funded by Australian Government Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
M.Tech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
Bachelor of Science in Textile Engineering
City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Consultant (Textile coloration, Defence textiles, Technical textiles)
Office: 512.01.12, 25, Dawson Street, Brunswick, Vic-3056, Australia
enr.anowar@yahoo.com +61 452209738, +8801788396264

Lecturer (study leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
Newcastle University College, Chittagong
Newcastle University College, Chittagong, Bangladesh
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
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Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
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Former Dyeing Officer, Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka

*** Discus about Hook and loop fastener ***

Ans: This item consists of two woven polyamide tapes, one covered with very fine hooks and the other with very fine loops. When pressed together they adhere securely to each other. This fastener used instead of chain or button. They are very strong against of shearing force, yet they peel apart easily when required to be unlock.

A ruin inventor made this, he offered this name is velcro. according to his name.

Hook

Loops

It is use only a limited number of garment like

- sports wear
- children wear
- Old-men dresses
- Medical textile
- Gloves and jacket.

Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain

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Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
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enr.anwar@yahoo.com +61 452209738, +8801788396264

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Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
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Write down the zipper components and its including the construction figure of zipper.

Ans:

Fig: Zipper

The components of zipper are describe below:

1. Tape: 100% polyester twill weave fabric are used to make the ground type of zipper
2. chain: Teeth chain made from metal or plastic. Metal teeth are made up of brass, Aluminium and plastic teeth are made by polyester, Nylon etc.

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

PhD Researcher (Technical Textiles), Thesis-final part
School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
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Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
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enr.anowar@yahoo.com +61 452209738, +8801788396264

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Newcastle University College, Chittagong
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Slidetz: It moves up and down. Function of slidetz is to engage or disengage the teeth of opposite slides of chain.

Top and bottom stop: They prevent the excessive up and down movement of slidetz. That is to say, they control the utmost and downmost movement of slidetz.

Pull tab: This is an additional part of a zipper. It is used for easy movement of slidetz in desired direction.

Q#4 What do you understand by label? Write down the classification of label?

Ans: Label is an attachment component of garments on which important information regarding the garments are written or printed. The most expensive labels are woven in a narrow width jacquard loom where as the cheaper labels are printed on woven fabric.

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

PhD Researcher (Technical Textiles), Thesis-final part
School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
(Funded by Australian Government Scholarship)
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Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
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Label

Main label

Sub label

Size label

Care label

Price label

Composition "

Main label: Main label contains brand

name/trade name of buyer, which is regis-
tered by the buyer. For example:

Levi's[®], Polo[®], Kiabi[®]
↓
American Arabian

Size label: It indicates the size of garments.

Such as: S, L, XL, XXL or collar length of shirt

15, 16, 16½ etc.

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

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Care label: It indicates the care instruction of garments by some internationally recognised sign. It shows washing, bleaching, drying, dry-cleaning, ironing condition etc.

Price label: It contains the price of garments.

Composition label: It indicates the fibre composition such as - 100% cotton, 65/35 TC etc etc.

*** Write down the symbol used for care label.

Ans: The internationally recognised care codes are expressed by the following 5 symbols.

① → washing condition

② → Bleaching

③ → Ironing

④ → Drying condition

⑤ → Dry cleaning condition

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

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School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
(Funded by Australian Government Scholarship)
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Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
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Former Dyeing Officer, Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka

Washing condition: To express washing conditions we use some internationally recognized symbols introduced by British. These are shown as below:

Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain

PhD Researcher (Technical Textiles), Thesis-final part
School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
(Funded by Australian Government Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
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Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying and Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka
Former Dyeing Officer, Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka

Bleaching condition: For extreming bleaching condition
the following symbols are used-

 → Suitable for chlorine bleaching.

 → Any bleaching is possible.

 → Do not bleach.

For ironing condition: Ironing condition is expressed by the following symbols.

 → use cool iron for ironing
(max^m temp. 110°C)

 → use warm iron (max^m temp 150°C)

 → use hot iron (max^m temp 200°C)

Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain

PhD Researcher (Technical Textiles), Thesis-final part
School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
(Funded by Australian Government Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
M.Tech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
Bachelor of Science in Textile Engineering
City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Consultant (Textile coloration, Defence textiles, Technical textiles)
Office: 512.01.12, 25, Dawson Street, Brunswick, Vic-3056, Australia
enr.anwar@yahoo.com +61 452209738, +8801788396264

Lecturer (study leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
Newcastle University College, Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former chief executive officer, Bangladesh textile and fashion, Uttara, Dhaka
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Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying and Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka
Former Dyeing Officer, Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka

Dry cleaning codes: The codes expressing dry cleaning condition are shown below.

(A) → Normal dry cleaning : All solvent can be use. (Petrol, tetrachloro ethylene, white spirit, hydrocarbon etc.)

(P) → Perchloroethylene, white spirit, solvent-113, solvent-11 can be use.

(F) → white spirit or solvent 113 can be use.

(X) → No dry cleaning is possible.

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

PhD Researcher (Technical Textiles), Thesis-final part
School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
(Funded by Australian Government Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
M.Tech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
Bachelor of Science in Textile Engineering
City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Consultant (Textile coloration, Defence textiles, Technical textiles)
Office: 512.01.12, 25, Dawson Street, Brunswick, Vic-3056, Australia
enr.anowar@yahoo.com +61 452209738, +8801788396264

Lecturer (study leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
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Newcastle University College, Chittagong
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Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying and Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka
Former Dyeing Officer, Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka

Drying condition: The care codes expressing drying condition are as below:

 → Garments can be tumble dry.

 → Hang dry.

 → Flat dry

 → Do not tumble dry.

Note:

Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain

PhD Researcher (Technical Textiles), Thesis-final part
School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
(Funded by Australian Government Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
M.Tech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
Bachelor of Science in Textile Engineering
City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Consultant (Textile coloration, Defence textiles, Technical textiles)
Office: 512.01.12, 25, Dawson Street, Brunswick, Vic-3056, Australia
engr.anwar@yahoo.com +61 452209738, +8801788396264

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City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
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BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
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*** what do you understand by interlining ***

Ans: Interlining: Interlinings are used to support, reinforce and control the shape of garments, such as collar, cuffs, waist band, hem, facing etc. There are two types.

1. Sewen interlining
2. Fusible interlining.

1. Sewen interlining: Sewen interlinings are made by sewing some plus of fabric together by sewing densely. Then it is joined with the main garment by sewing.

2. Fusible interlinings: Fusible interlining have coating of thermoplastic material / resin coating on them and are joined to garments by adhering them with the help of pressure and heat fusible interlining give better result than that of sewn ones.

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

PhD Researcher (Technical Textiles), Thesis-final part
School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
(Funded by Australian Government Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
M.Tech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
Bachelor of Science in Textile Engineering
City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Consultant (Textile coloration, Defence textiles, Technical textiles)
Office: 512.01.12, 25, Dawson Street, Brunswick, Vic-3056, Australia
engr.anowar@yahoo.com +61 452209738, +8801788396264

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City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
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BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
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Newcastle University College, Chittagong
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Types of fusible interlining: Fusible interlining etc.
various types.

- (1) Poly ethylene coated interlining
- (2) Polypropylene coated interlining.
- (3) Polyamide coated interlining.
- (4) Polyester coated interlining.
- (5) PVC (Poly vinyl chloride)
- (6) PVA (Poly vinyl Acetate coating interlining)

Property of fusible interlining: The fusible interlining must provide the following property.

1. For fusing temp. the fabric colour must be keep stable, it should not be degrade. Fusing temp should not be more than 175°C
2. Minimum fusing temp. should be such that during washing, the bond between fabric and interlining should not be break. Fusing temp must not less than 110°C.

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

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Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
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enr.anowar@yahoo.com +61 452209738, +8801788396264

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(3) Bond between interlining and fabric should not be damaged during washing and dry cleaning.

(4) After attaching interlining the fabric must achieve proper strength and handle property.

5. Interlining colours should be transparent or if necessary it can be coloured. The fabric colour should not be mismatched with other colour part due to attaching interlining.

6. The coating of interlining must not be harmful to health.

*** Write down the method of resin coatings.

- (1) Scatter coating
- (2) Dry dot coating
- (3) Paste coating
- (4) Film coating
- (5) Emulsion coating

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

PhD Researcher (Technical Textiles), Thesis-final part
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Emulsion coating: In this process resin powder is mixed with water and chemical and made emulsion. Now the bare fabric is pass through the emulsion and then it is squeezed by roller to remove excess emulsion. So the fabric absorb emulsion. Then the emulsified fabric is passed through woven. In a woven form heating arrangement the resin coating is attached on both side of fabric uniformly. Then it is dry and we get our required coating of interlining.

Write down the advantages of fusible interlining over sewen interlining.

- Ans:
- (1) Fusible interlining taken shorten manufacturing time with a consequent reduction in labour cost other than sewing interlining.
 - (2) Reduction in skill required compared with sewen interlining, so this leads reduction of training time.

Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain

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Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
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(3) It is easier to achieve consistent quality than woven interlining especially on modern light weight garments.

(4) The garments which are produced by fusible interlining have better aesthetic property and quality than woven interlining.

(5) It is available in market than woven interlining.

What do you understand by pressing?

Ans: The process by which the unwanted creases and wrinkles are removed from the garments and the outlook of the garments is improved, is known as pressing. It also called ironing. In garments industry there is a separate section for ironing the product. It is generally done by heated plates and electric ironing moist condition of garments.

Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain

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School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
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Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTEchin Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
Bachelor of Science in Textile Engineering
City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Consultant (Textile coloration, Defence textiles, Technical textiles)
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engr.anwar@yahoo.com +61 452209738, +8801788396264

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Newcastle University College, Chittagong
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Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying and Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka
Former Dyeing Officer, Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka

~~***~~ Write down the objects of preming

Ans:

1. Removal of unwanted creases and wrinkles:

During garments manufacturing, creasing and crumpling occur due to handling and for tying up garments tightly. To remove this creases and wrinkles preming is done.

2. Hiding imperfection: Preming can hide garments imperfections and faults such as puckered seam, nepp etc

3. To apply creases where it necessary: Sometimes in garments we need to apply some permanent creases, such as pleats in shirt and for that purpose we apply crease by preming.

Dart → Double crease

Pleat → Single crease

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

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(Funded by Australian Government Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
M.Tech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
Bachelor of Science in Textile Engineering
City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Consultant (Textile coloration, Defence textiles, Technical textiles)
Office: 512.01.12, 25, Dawson Street, Brunswick, Vic-3056, Australia
engr.anowar@yahoo.com +61 452209738, +8801788396264

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City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
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BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
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Newcastle University College, Chittagong
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Former Dyeing Officer, Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka

4. Shaping: Dart and pleats are used to make garments to fit properly with the shape of human body.

To make this dart more attractive pressing is applied which is known as shaping.

5. Underpressing: Sometime pressing is done before sewing the garment to create some wrinkle, gathering effect in garment and then perform sewing. This types of pressing is known as under pressing.

But they also require final pressing.

6. Final pressing: Final pressing is to position the garments after manufacturing. By final pressing gloss or glaze is induced on garments, to achieve a firm edge or seam. It also flattens the surface fibre heavily.

gloss - চকচক

Flattens → সতত

Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain

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Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
M.Tech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
Bachelor of Science in Textile Engineering
City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Consultant (Textile coloration, Defence textiles, Technical textiles)
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enr.anwar@yahoo.com +61 452209738, +8801788396264

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Newcastle University College, Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
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Former Dyeing Officer, Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka

*** Discuss about pressing equipments ***

For various garments various types of pressing may be appropriate. Among those in garments industry the following pressing m/c's are used.

1. Steam iron

2. Buck pressing iron.

Steam iron: For steam iron, the iron is heated up by steam which is supplied from a central boiler. The supply of steam is regulated by a hand regulated button. These iron are triangular in shape and their weight varies from 1-10 kg.

For pressing with this iron, ironing bed or table is required. For this bed, there should be provision of air-suction. After ironing a foot regulated switch is pressed for the air suction which removes the moisture and heat from the pressed garments quickly.

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

PhD Researcher (Technical Textiles), Thesis-final part
School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
(Funded by Australian Government Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
M.Tech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
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City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Consultant (Textile coloration, Defence textiles, Technical textiles)
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enr.anowar@yahoo.com +61 452209738, +8801788396264

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Write down the properties of sewing thread.

Ans: Properties of sewing threads are given below:

(1) Tensile strength: Tensile strength is the energy needed to break a thread. It will vary slightly according to condition, i.e. humidity temperature, rate of applying load etc. It is expressed by kg, gm, lb etc.

(2) Tenacity: Tenacity is the relative strength of a thread obtained by dividing the tensile strength by thickness. Tenacity indicates thread strength to its unit thickness. It is expressed by gm/tex, gm/denier.

(3) Loop strength: Loop strength is the load required to break a length of thread which is looped through another loop of thread of same length.

Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain

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School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
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Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
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Bachelor of Science in Textile Engineering
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enr.anwar@yahoo.com +61 452209738, +8801788396264

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Newcastle University College, Chittagong
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(4) Loop strength ratio: The ratio between the strength of single thread and loop strength of that thread, is known as loop strength ratio. The efficiency of thread is measured by this.

$$\text{Loop strength ratio} = \frac{\text{Loop strength}}{\text{Single yarn strength}}$$

(5) Minimum loop strength: The most weak loop strength in continuous loop series is called minimum loop strength. Minimum loop strength is used to know the performance of thread in a continuous stitch.

(6) Elongation at break: At the time of thread breaking (when force is applied) the length, which is expanded from its original length, is called elongation at break. It is expressed as percentage.

(7) Stress-strain curve: If we plot increasing thread tenacity, against elongation a curve is obtained, which is known as stress-strain curve. To compare two thread it is an advantageous process.

Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain

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School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
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Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
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Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

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enr.anowar@yahoo.com +61 452209738, +8801788396264

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of sewing thread. Its shrinkage occurs in sewing thread, seam pucker will form, which is a serious fault in garment. It expressed as percentage.

(10) Abraction resistance: The resistance against abraction is important to compare sewing performance. For determining sewing thread property the abraction resistance of two same thread is preferable.

(11) Colour fastness: The colour of a thread should be lasting as long as fabric/garments and the thread colour don't bleed to other parts of fabric. Colour fastness means after washing or other after exposed to sunlight the thread colour is not faded.

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

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Authorship

Sole authorship of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

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Anowar 12.05.2023

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, MTech
PhD Researcher, ID: 3820066
(Funded by Australian Government Scholarship)
School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University
512.01.12, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick
Vic-3056, Australia.

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

PhD Researcher (Technical Textiles), Thesis-final part
School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
(Funded by Australian Government Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
M.Tech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
Bachelor of Science in Textile Engineering
City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Consultant (Textile coloration, Defence textiles, Technical textiles)
Office: 512.01.12, 25, Dawson Street, Brunswick, Vic-3056, Australia
engr.anowar@yahoo.com +61 452209738, +8801788396264

Lecturer (study leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
Newcastle University College, Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former chief executive officer, Bangladesh textile and fashion, Uttara, Dhaka
Former product developer and coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd.
Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying and Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka
Former Dyeing Officer, Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka

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Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

PhD Researcher (Technical Textiles), Thesis-final part
School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
(Funded by Australian Government Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
M.Tech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
Bachelor of Science in Textile Engineering
City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Consultant (Textile coloration, Defence textiles, Technical textiles)
Office: 512.01.12, 25, Dawson Street, Brunswick, Vic-3056, Australia
enr.anowar@yahoo.com +61 452209738, +8801788396264

Lecturer (study leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
Newcastle University College, Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former chief executive officer, Bangladesh textile and fashion, Uttara, Dhaka
Former product developer and coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd.
Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying and Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka
Former Dyeing Officer, Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka

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Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

PhD Researcher (Technical Textiles), Thesis-final part
School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
(Funded by Australian Government Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
M.Tech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
Bachelor of Science in Textile Engineering
City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Consultant (Textile coloration, Defence textiles, Technical textiles)
Office: 512.01.12, 25, Dawson Street, Brunswick, Vic-3056, Australia
engr.anowar@yahoo.com +61 452209738, +8801788396264

Lecturer (study leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
Newcastle University College, Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former chief executive officer, Bangladesh textile and fashion, Uttara, Dhaka
Former product developer and coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd.
Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying and Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka
Former Dyeing Officer, Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka

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Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

PhD Researcher (Technical Textiles), Thesis-final part
School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
(Funded by Australian Government Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
M.Tech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
Bachelor of Science in Textile Engineering
City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Consultant (Textile coloration, Defence textiles, Technical textiles)
Office: 512.01.12, 25, Dawson Street, Brunswick, Vic-3056, Australia
enr.anowar@yahoo.com +61 452209738, +8801788396264

Lecturer (study leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
Newcastle University College, Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former chief executive officer, Bangladesh textile and fashion, Uttara, Dhaka
Former product developer and coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd.
Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying and Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka
Former Dyeing Officer, Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka

University.

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Hossain, M. A. (2023e). *Anowar's Handbook of Electrical and Electronics Engineering*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13624.72966>;

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Hossain, M. A. (2023k). *Anowar's Handbook on Elements of Mechanical Engineering*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.25368.78089>

Hossain, M. A. (2023l). *Anowar's Handbook on Elements of Theory of Machine and Machine Design*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28724.22405>

Hossain, M. A. (2023m). *Anowar's Handbook on Environment and Safety Management*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

PhD Researcher (Technical Textiles), Thesis-final part
School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
(Funded by Australian Government Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
M.Tech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
Bachelor of Science in Textile Engineering
City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Consultant (Textile coloration, Defence textiles, Technical textiles)
Office: 512.01.12, 25, Dawson Street, Brunswick, Vic-3056, Australia
enr.anowar@yahoo.com +61 452209738, +8801788396264

Lecturer (study leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
Newcastle University College, Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former chief executive officer, Bangladesh textile and fashion, Uttara, Dhaka
Former product developer and coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd.
Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying and Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka
Former Dyeing Officer, Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka

- 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36273.97126>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023n). *Anowar's Handbook on Fabric Structure and Design*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.30821.37606>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240534>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023o). *Anowar's Handbook on Yarn Manufacturing Technology (Part-01)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19896.52484>
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- Hossain, M. A. (2023t). *Camouflage textiles with technical coloration incorporating illumination under multidimensional combat backgrounds, PhD student: 3820066, Second milestone thesis for the degree of doctor of philosophy* [Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick Campus, Melbourne, Vic-3056, Australia, 2022]. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15701.50403>, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7898707>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023u). *Camouflage textiles with technical coloration incorporating illumination, PhD student: 3820066, First milestone thesis for the degree of doctor of philosophy* [Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick Campus, Melbourne, Vic-3056, Australia, 2021]. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15701.50403>, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7898541>

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

PhD Researcher (Technical Textiles), Thesis-final part
School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
(Funded by Australian Government Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
M.Tech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
Bachelor of Science in Textile Engineering
City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Consultant (Textile coloration, Defence textiles, Technical textiles)
Office: 512.01.12, 25, Dawson Street, Brunswick, Vic-3056, Australia
enr.anowar@yahoo.com +61 452209738, +8801788396264

Lecturer (study leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
Newcastle University College, Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
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Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying and Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka
Former Dyeing Officer, Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka

- Hossain, M. A. (2023v). Coloration of polyamide-6,6 fabric with carbon black nano particle for camouflage textiles of simultaneous spectrum probe in visible and near infrared. *Preprint (Version 1) available at Research Square* <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-2686707/v1>
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Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

PhD Researcher (Technical Textiles), Thesis-final part
School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
(Funded by Australian Government Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTEchin Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
Bachelor of Science in Textile Engineering
City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Consultant (Textile coloration, Defence textiles, Technical textiles)
Office: 512.01.12, 25, Dawson Street, Brunswick, Vic-3056, Australia
engr.anowar@yahoo.com +61 452209738, +8801788396264

Lecturer (study leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
Newcastle University College, Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former chief executive officer, Bangladesh textile and fashion, Uttara, Dhaka
Former product developer and coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd.
Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying and Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka
Former Dyeing Officer, Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka

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Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

PhD Researcher (Technical Textiles), Thesis-final part
School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
(Funded by Australian Government Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTEchin Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
Bachelor of Science in Textile Engineering
City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Consultant (Textile coloration, Defence textiles, Technical textiles)
Office: 512.01.12, 25, Dawson Street, Brunswick, Vic-3056, Australia
engr.anowar@yahoo.com +61 452209738, +8801788396264

Lecturer (study leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
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Newcastle University College, Chittagong
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Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying and Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka
Former Dyeing Officer, Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka

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Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

PhD Researcher (Technical Textiles), Thesis-final part
School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
(Funded by Australian Government Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
M.Tech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
Bachelor of Science in Textile Engineering
City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
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Office: 512.01.12, 25, Dawson Street, Brunswick, Vic-3056, Australia
enr.anowar@yahoo.com +61 452209738, +8801788396264

Lecturer (study leave), Department of Textile Engineering
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Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying and Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka
Former Dyeing Officer, Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka

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